

INTEGRATED APPROACH TO THE TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC PYELONEPHRITIS

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The actuality of issue.

Chronic pyelonephritis (CP) is one of the most common diseases, often relapsing, latent course. In many women, pyelonephritis during pregnancy is the first clinical manifestation of this latent disease. Along with the high prevalence, it should be noted that this is also due to the anatomical and functional features of the female body. As well as the development of resistance of microorganisms to antibacterial drugs is a major problem in the treatment. In this connection, the problem of treating patients with chronic pyelonephritis remains one of the most urgent in the field of internal diseases.

Purpose of the research.

The purpose of the study was to study the effectiveness of complex treatment of CP using ozone therapy with immunocorrective therapy with combination of basic treatment of patients with chronic pyelonephritis.

Material and methods.

The study involved 43 pregnant women with CP, aged 20 to 35 years. Examination of pregnant women was carried out, including clinical (questionnaire of complaints, questioning, objective examination), laboratory (complete blood count, urinalysis, urinalysis according to Nechiporenko, urine culture, biochemical tests) and instrumental (ultrasound) research methods.

Among the examined women, the first group consisted of pregnant women (n=14) receiving basic therapy. The second group of 13 pregnant women with CP received ozone therapy with combination of traditional therapy (basic treatment + 400 ml of saline solution ozonated to an ozone concentration in the liquid of 4 mg/l, intravenously, drip, every other day, 5 times). The third group of 15 pregnant women with CP - with traditional therapy received ozone therapy and immunocorrective therapy with polyoxidonium (basic treatment + ozone therapy + polyoxidonium 6 mg intravenously, 5 times).

Results of the research.

As a result of the treatment, clinical indicators, complaints, objective status data and laboratory parameters were analyzed before and after the therapy in the comparison groups. All women during the period of exacerbation had dysuria, pain in the lumbar region, fever, massive leukocyturia, bacteriuria, as well as ultrasonic changes characteristic of a chronic inflammatory process in the kidneys.

Analysis of clinical and laboratory efficacy showed that in the examined three groups there was a clinical improvement in the general condition of patients. Thus, lower back pain decreased by 85.71%, 92.31% and 93.33%, respectively, both in the first, second and third groups. Indicators such as dysuria decreased by 92.85%, 92% and 93% (respectively in the first, second and third groups). Leukocyturia significantly decreased on the fifth day by 71.43%, 84.62%, 86.67% (in the first, second and third groups, respectively). The results of eradication indicators of pathogens after treatment in combination with traditional therapy with ozone and immunocorrective therapy were significantly better than in the group with ozone therapy with combination of traditional therapy and in the traditional treatment group (86.6%, 84.6% and 64.28% respectively).

Conclusions.

Based on the above, the appointment of pregnant women with chronic pyelonephritis against the background of traditional treatment with ozone therapy and immunocorrective therapy is an appropriate and effective method of treatment.